

Studies on Tensile Behaviour and Uniformity of Jute Plied Yarn

Palash Paul^{1*} & Asis Mukhopadhyay²

1. Office of the Development Officer, University of North Bengal, West Bengal, India
2. Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, West Bengal, India

Abstract:

Jute plied yarns are primarily used as sewing twine for sacks, apart from their other uses in carpet, geotextiles, etc. Though tensile behaviour and uniformity are the two most important properties of jute-plied yarns, studies on the factors that influence these properties are not available. In the present work, the authors studied the influence of the number of plies, single yarn twist factor and ply to single yarn twist ratio on tenacity and breaking extension of jute plied yarn. It is observed that with increase in the number of plies, the optimum tenacity of jute plied yarn is achieved at comparatively lower ply to single twist ratio. They also noticed that breaking extension of jute ply yarn increases with increase in the number of plies as well as ply to single twist ratio. While studying the irregularity of jute plied yarn, they observed that plying improves jute yarn regularity and maximum improvement is observed in 4-ply yarn followed by 3-ply and 2-ply.

Keywords: irregularity, jute, plied yarn, tenacity, twist factor, twist ratio

*Corresponding Author:

Mr. Palash Paul
Development Officer
Office of the Development Officer
University of North Bengal
Darjeeling - 734 013
E-mail: palash@nbu.ac.in

1. Introduction:

Although single yarns are used in most textile applications, this type of yarn possesses comparatively higher hairiness, lower abrasion resistance, higher unevenness and most importantly, lower specific strength and elongation [1,2]. These factors not only contribute to the aesthetic appearance but also influence the functional performance of the yarns and fabrics made thereof.

A plied or folded yarn is produced by twisting two or more single yarns together. Despite of the fact that twisting adds cost to the yarn, plying is sometimes inevitable where single yarn properties cannot fulfil the end-use requirement of the product. Although further processing like sizing to improve weavability of warps, waxing to increase abrasion resistance of knitted yarns, singeing to remove unwanted surface hairiness etc. are practiced to overcome some of the deficiencies of single yarns [3], plying is exclusively done to achieve special properties of yarn and/or fabric which have no alternative method to achieve.

Studies show that while multiple strands of single yarns are twisted together the longitudinal variations in the individual yarns are balanced and spot defects are compensated [2]. Studies also show that plying two or more single yarns improves vital yarn properties like strength, elongation, evenness, hairiness, abrasion resistance, bulkiness, etc. [4-6].

Extensive studies have been conducted to understand properties of plied yarn made out of cotton and other major types of textile fibres [1-7]. Omerglu [7] observed that hairiness values of plied yarn, made out of ring spun cotton single yarns, decreased as twist levels increased with evidence of greater influence of ply twist than single twist. Sett, Mukherjee and Kundu [4] observed that the tenacity of Z on Z plied yarn is higher than S on Z plied yarn. The authors also observed that tenacity of S on Z plied yarn decreases with increase in single yarn twist level but in case of Z on Z plied yarn it gradually increases to maximum level and then decreases with further increase in single yarn twist. Coulson & Dakin [8] opined that for all values of singles twist there is a best doubling twist at which maximum strength can be obtained. In general, the maximum strength obtainable from the doubled yarn decreases as the singles twist increases. The strongest doubled yarn of any count can be obtained by using single yarns of low twist level with high doubling twist.

Like cotton and other textiles, jute yarns are also plied, particularly for its end-use as sewing threads, carpets, fancy yarns, etc. Although it is reported that the performance of jute sewing thread plays great role on the serviceability of jute sacks, studies on structure-property relations of jute plied yarns are limited. Moreover, considering the fact that jute fibres are distinctive and its processing technology are different from conventional textiles process, this necessitates a comprehensive study to understand the physical and mechanical characteristics of jute plied yarn in order to optimize parameters to achieve a quality plied yarn. Effort in this work has been made to understand effects of various ply yarn parameters on its properties.

2. Materials and Methods:

To study the effect of single yarn as well as plied yarns' structural parameters on properties of plied yarn, 27 different types of plied yarns of 930 tex resultant count were produced by varying single yarn count in three levels (233 tex, 310 tex and 465 tex), single yarn twist factor (TF) in three levels (24, 26 and 28 in tpc-tex unit) and plied to single twist ratio in three levels (0.5, 0.7 and 0.9). All the yarn samples were prepared from TD4 quality raw jute (as per Indian Standard No. IS 271: 2003) in pilot machines following norm-based machine parameters. The detailed set parameters for singles and plied yarn are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Single and Ply yarn parameters

Plied yarn count (tex)	930			930			930		
No. of ply x single yarn count (tex)	4 x 233			3 x 310			2 x 465		
Single yarn twist factor (in tpc - tex unit)	24	26	28	24	26	28	24	26	28
Ply to single twist ratio (D:S)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

In order to independently study the dependancy of plied yarn tenacity on number of plies as well as to understand the optimum ply to single twist ratio (D:S) which yields maximum plied yarn tenacity, plied yarn samples were prepared varying combinations of number of plies from two to four and five levels D:S from 0.5 to 0.9 with increment of 0.1. To rule out effect of single yarn twist in this case, only singles prepared using twist factor of 24 were considered.

For experimentation and analysis purposes, 3-factors and 3-levels Box–Behnken experimental design was used to plot response surfaces using Minitab statistical software. The factors and levels used for experimentation purpose are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Box–Behnken Design of Experiments

Factors	Levels		
	- 1	0	1
No. of Ply	2	3	4
Single yarn twist factor (in tpc - tex unit)	24	26	28
Ply to single twist ratio (D:S)	0.5	0.7	0.9

The tensile properties of single as well as plied yarns were tested as per ASTM D2256 in Instron UTM in a testing laboratory accredited as per ISO/IEC 17025. Average of ten observations for a particular quality of yarn was considered for analysis purpose. Uniformity of the yarns was tested in Premier Uniformity Tester as per ASTM D1425. Three observations were made for each quality of yarn.

3. Results and Discussion:

Test results obtained from the experimental yarns were assessed for determining influence of the parameters on tensile and uniformity of plied yarn, two most important property requirements. Such effects are described below:

i. Influence of number of ply and ply to single twist ratio on plied yarn tenacity:

In order to understand the dependency of number of ply and ply to single twist ratio (D:S) on the tenacity of plied yarn, tenacity of multi-ply yarns are plotted against five levels of D:S which is given in Fig. 1. From the plot it can be observed that irrespective of number of plies in the folded yarn, ply yarn tenacity increases with initial increase in D:S and then starts falling, keeping an intermediate optimum level of D:S. The initial rise in tenacity may be attributed from better binding of single yarns within the ply as a result of increased twist level. Such binding may enable the constituent single yarns to share stress equally, rather than distinctive stress sharing by single yarns in case of loosely twisted plied yarn. The fall in tenacity after the optimum D:S may be due to prominent obliquity effect, as the phenomenon observed in multifilament yarns.

Figure 1: Ply tenacity (cN/tex) vs. no. of ply and ply to single twist ratio

It can also be seen from the plot that with increase in the number of plies, the optimum tenacity of the folded yarn can be obtained at lower D:S. The same behaviour may be explained by the findings of Huang et. al. [9] who narrated that interaction forces are generated between the single yarns during the axial-tensile process of a ply yarn. The authors derived following relation to define the frictional resistance (f_y) by the single yarns which contribute to the plied yarn strength

$$f_y = \mu N + \alpha S$$

Where, μ is the friction coefficient, N is the radial pressure, α is the cohesion coefficient, S is the contact area.

Considering the above relation, since each single yarn touches the neighbouring yarns, contact area between the single yarns' thereby increases with increase in the number of plies. As a result, 4-ply yarns having four contact lines/areas among single yarns as a whole may lead to higher frictional resistance and thereby higher tenacity. In contrary, with 2-ply yarn there exist only one contact line/area, and thus, less contribution to yarn strength.

ii. Influence of single yarn twist factor and number of ply on plied yarn tenacity:

Contour plot of plied yarn tenacity with respect to no. of plies and single yarn TF at a fixed D:S is given in Fig. 2. From the plot it is evident that out of these two parameters, no. of plies is the most dominating factor for plied yarn tenacity, as with increase in number of plies for any level of singles' TF, the tenacity increases significantly. In contrary, single yarn TF influences ply tenacity only when number of ply is less (2 or 3 in this case), but has minimal effect for higher number of plies. In this instant case, a 4-ply yarn showed highest tenacity (>11.5 cN/tex) for all three levels of single yarn TF, whereas, tenacity of 2-ply yarn was least (~10 cN/tex) when single yarns' TF was 24 and increased up to 11 cN/tex sequentially with increase in singles' TF to 28.

Figure 2: Ply tenacity (cN/tex) vs. single yarn TF and no. of ply

iii. Influence of single yarn twist factor and ply to single twist ratio on plied yarn tenacity:

Fig. 3 below shows the tenacity contour plot of a 3-ply yarn with respect to single yarn TF and ply to single (D:S) twist ratio. The plot shows that when the other parameters are kept fixed, both singles' and ply twist effect ply yarn tenacity. While an increase in singles' TF, the ply tenacity steadily increases, the later however increases first with increase in D:S and starts falling in case of further increase in D:S. The optimum value of ply tenacity is achieved somewhere with higher singles' TF but with low to medium D:S. To analyze the behaviour, dependency of single yarn's strength with respect to the above three levels of TF was studied and it was observed that single yarn strength of jute yarn was increased with increase in TF level. This trend of rise in singles' strength with TF may have influenced ply tenacity increment.

Figure 3: Ply tenacity (cN/tex) vs. single yarn TF and D:S

iv. Jute plied yarn breaking extension:

Jute fibre possesses high modulus and low breaking extension [10] and consequently jute yarns are less extensive. Behaviour of plied yarn breaking extension has been studied in this work and plots with respect to the considered parameters are given in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Jute plied yarn breaking extension with respect to no. of ply, single yarn TF and D:S

Graphs show that plied yarn breaking extension is mostly dependent on number of ply and ply to single twist ratio, and it increases with increase in the number of plies as well as D:S. Increase of ply extension due to increase in D:S may be attributed from higher obliquity of single yarns in ply structure.

v. Uniformity of jute plied yarn:

With high variability of jute fibre length, jute yarns produced in the conventional system possess high irregularity. Fig. 5 below shows the mass irregularity (U%) of single jute yarns prepared at 26 twist factor and plied yarns tested in capacitance type yarn evenness tester and Table 3 shows corresponding thick (+50%) and thin places (-50%) per km in the single as well as plied yarns.

Figure 5: Mass irregularity of single and ply yarn

Table 3: Thick and Thin places in yarns

Ply type	Thick places (+50%) / km		Thin places (-50%) / km	
	In single yarn before plying	In plied yarn	In single yarn before plying	In plied yarn
4-ply	1360	210	1970	40
3-ply	1440	180	1560	130
2-ply	830	510	600	160

The general principle of improvement in yarn evenness due to folding also holds good for jute yarn as it can be seen from the Fig. 5. Irrespective of number of plies, jute ply yarn shows significant improvement in yarn regularity, which may be due to doubling effect and thereby compensation of thick and thin places. Table 4 also justifies that plying compensates thick and thin places present in single yarns. Although single yarn of 233 tex shows highest U% as compared to other single yarns, while these yarns are folded to get a desired count of ply yarn, the improvement is also highest as compared to other yarns. This is due to effect of 4 plies as compared to 3 ply and 2 ply for 310 tex and 465 tex single yarns respectively. Ply to single twist ratio, however, plays insignificant role as far as ply yarn evenness is concerned.

4. Conclusions:

Efforts in this work have been made to understand effects of various parameters of tensile and uniformity of jute plied yarn. Based on the study, the following conclusions are made –

- Irrespective of number of plies in the folded yarn, jute ply yarn tenacity increases with initial increase in ply to single twist ratio and then starts falling. However, with increase in the number of plies, the optimum tenacity of the folded yarn can be achieved at comparative lower ply to single twist ratio.
- Tenacity of jute plied yarn increases with increase in the number of plies. Moreover, tenacity of 2 and 3 ply jute yarns can be enhanced by using single yarns of comparatively high twist factor.

- Jute ply yarn breaking extension increases with increase in the number of plies as well as ply to single twist ratio.
- Irrespective of number of plies, jute ply yarn shows general tendency of improvement in yarn regularity. The improvement is maximum for 4-ply yarn followed by 3-ply and 2-ply
- Thick and thin places present in single jute yarns are also compensated after plying. This may also be one of the reasons for increase in jute yarn tenacity after plying.

References:

- [1] K. Palaniswamy and P. Mohamed, "Effect of the single-yarn twist and ply to single-yarn twist ratio on the hairiness and abrasion resistance of cotton two-ply yarn," *AUTEX Research Journal*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 59 - 71, 2006.
- [2] O. Ozdemir, S. Sardag and F. Kalaouglu, "Effects of twisting methods on plied yarn properties," *Indian Journal of Fibre and Textile Research*, vol. 31, pp. 394 - 400, 2006
- [3] D. E. A. Plate and J. Lappage, "An alternate approach to two-fold weaving yarn – Part I – Control of surface fibres," *Journal of the Textile Institute*, vol. 3, no. 99-106, 1982
- [4] S. K. Sett, A. Mukherjee and N. Kundu, "Influence of twist on tensile and abrasion properties of DREF-II friction spun plied yarns," *American International Journal of Research in Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 52 - 56, 2014.
- [5] P. H. Brorens, J. Lappage, J. Bedford and S. L. Ranford, "Studies on the Abrasion Resistance of Weaving Yarns," *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, vol. 812, pp. 126 - 134, 1990.
- [6] S. Dhamija, A. Chowdhury and R. Chattopadhyay, "Effect of Ply Twist Factor on Hairiness and Unevenness of Two Plied Cotton Yarns Made of Different Spinning Technologies," *Journal of the Institute of Engineers (India)*, vol. June, 2016.
- [7] S. Omeroglu, "An investigation on the effects of ply and single twists on strength, hairiness and abrasion resistance properties of two-ply cotton ring-spun yarns," *Tekstil ve Konfeksiyon*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 204 - 212, 2013
- [8] A. F. W. Coulson and G. Dakin, "Doubled Yarns. Part I. the influence of twist on the strength and certain other properties of two-fold yarns," *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, vol. 48, no. 7-8, pp. T207 - T232, 1957
- [9] Huang, W., Fu, T., Zhang, Y. and Wang, J., 2017. An approach to predict the tensile strength of a two-ply yarn from single filament yarn. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 108(3), pp.412-417
- [10] Virk, A.S., Hall, W. and Summerscales, J., 2009. Tensile properties of jute fibres. *Materials Science and Technology*, 25(10), pp.1289-1295